

MultiXscale

Software release of lattice-gas simulation modules for PyStencils/waLBerla

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Executive Summary

Electrochemical double layer capacitors, often called supercapacitors, are energy storage systems which accumulate and release energy through reversible ion adsorption at electrode/electrolyte interfaces. Porous carbons are commonly used as electrode materials due to their relatively low cost and good electronic conductivity. Over the past decade, most of the simulations of supercapacitors were performed at the microscopic scale, using molecular dynamics software such as Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) and Extensible Simulation Package for Research on Soft Matter Systems (ESPResSo). This allowed to understand the adsorption of ions and the effect of surface porosity on some electrochemical properties. However it is well known from experiments that commercial materials are highly inhomogeneous. For example, the typical pore size distributions of the best performing carbons range from 0.8 to 2 nm. Molecular simulations, where electrode sizes are a few nanometers, only allow for the inclusion of a few pores. It is therefore necessary to simulate electrodes and supercapacitors at larger scales. To this end, Lattice Porous Carbon 3D (LPC3D) is a software designed for mesoscopic simulations of capacitive properties of carbon-carbon capacitors, based on a lattice-gas model. The code calculates properties such as quantities of adsorbed ions, diffusion coefficients and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectra for ions (or other species) adsorbed in porous carbon matrices. It uses information from molecular dynamics simulations as its main input, so that the parameterization is made at the microscale.

Before the start of the MultiXscale project, LPC3D was available as an open-source serial code, written in C. It allowed to conduct simulations of ions or solvent molecules diffusing in a single carbon particle or a particle in contact with a limited amount of bulk electrolyte.

Figure 1: Systems which could be simulated using LPC3D before the MultiXscale project and with the current implementation.

Thanks to the MultiXscale project, and in particular the work reported here, LPC3D is now available as an open-source parallel code, which can be run on CPU and GPU, written using PyStencils which generates optimised C++ code. PyStencils is a companion package of the highly parallel waLBerla designed to conduct Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). The new implementation allows to conduct simulations on several particles in contact with an electrolyte [1] and full supercapacitors, fulfilling the objective of Task 2.5 of MultiXscale.

This report describes the basics of the lattice-gas model considered, its implementation using PyStencils, and its application to the simulation of a full supercapacitor.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable aims at providing information on the implementation of the lattice-gas simulation code `LPC3D`, using `PyStencils`, and its computational performance. It is delivered at the same time as the public release, as an open-source code, of `LPC3D` which is now available at <https://github.com/multixscale/LPC3D>.

This report contains elements relevant to Task 2.5 - Optimising scalability of the lattice-gas method for large-scale simulations of energy materials - lead by Sorbonne Université.

1.2 Target audience

This report is intended for readers with technical expertise in High Performance Computing (HPC) and knowledge in lattice-gas or lattice-Boltzmann simulations, such as users and developers of `PyStencils/walBer1a`. While potential users might be interested in some of the information about the underlying equations of the model and benchmarking results, specific information about the scientific importance of the model and about how to setup calculations are better described in published works (such as [1]) and in the user manual (available in the GitHub repository).

1.3 Report outline

In Section 2, we outline the main features of the lattice-gas model. We give the main equations describing the diffusion of species through the lattice and explain how the model is parameterised.

In Section 3, we describe the implementation of the model using `PyStencils` and show performance results.

In Section 4, we discuss an application of the new implementation on the case of a full supercapacitor.

Lastly, in the conclusion, we outline the connection with Tasks 3.3 and 4.2, in which the plan is to couple the lattice-gas model with an on-the-fly calculation of microscopic properties, in a more accurate way than currently done, with either Molecular Density Functional Theory (MDFT) or molecular dynamics simulations using `LAMMPS`.

2 Lattice simulations of electrolyte species in porous carbon particles

2.1 Overview of the lattice-gas model

In the lattice model considered, each lattice site is either a pore or a volume of liquid for which several values need to be defined: i) a pore size (or size of the volume of liquid), ii) an energy (related to the quantities of ions or species in the site), iii) a resonant frequency (for the calculation of NMR spectra). The pore sizes are typically assigned following experimental pore size distributions [2–5] or pore size distributions of atomistic structures [6, 7]. The site energies are usually selected following independent molecular dynamics simulations corresponding to the correct electrolyte. The resonant frequencies are extracted from Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations [8, 9]. In specific cases, all these quantities can also be assigned arbitrarily to study systematically the effects of various parameters [1, 7]

2.2 Motion of electrolyte species through the lattice

At every timestep Δt , the electrolyte species, present in the lattice sites, attempt to perform a step to any of their nearest neighbours (6 for a three-dimensional simple cubic lattice). The conditional probability to accept a move from site i to site j , $p_{acc}(i \rightarrow j)$, which is not necessarily equal to the probability of accepting the reverse move, $p_{acc}(j \rightarrow i)$, is:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{acc}(i \rightarrow j) &= \exp\left(\frac{-(E_j - E_i)}{k_B T}\right) \quad \text{if } E_j > E_i \\ &= 1 \quad \text{if } E_j \leq E_i \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature of the system. As a consequence, the larger $E_j - E_i$ the less likely a particle is to jump from i to j . With these rules, the probability of a particle to visit site i will be given by the Boltzmann distribution:

$$\rho_i = \langle \rho \rangle \times \frac{\exp\left(\frac{-E_i}{k_B T}\right)}{\sum_j \exp\left(\frac{-E_j}{k_B T}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where ρ_i is the average density at site i and $\langle \rho \rangle$ is the density averaged over all lattice sites.

It is worth noting that most calculations are started with the densities of particles in sites directly equal to the Boltzmann averages but that it is possible to start from a non-equilibrium situation.

2.3 Calculation of diffusion coefficients in the lattice-gas model

Diffusion coefficients are typically calculated using a Green-Kubo relation that relates the Velocity AutoCorrelation Functions (VACF) to the self-diffusion coefficients:

$$D = \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{d} \langle \mathbf{v}(0) \cdot \mathbf{v}(t) \rangle dt \quad (3)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient, d is the dimensionality of the system, $\mathbf{v}(0)$ is the velocity at time $t = 0$, $\mathbf{v}(t)$ is the velocity at time t and $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes an average over all particles and all trajectories. Here we use the discrete equivalent of Eqn. 3 (see reference [2] for details of the derivation):

$$D = \frac{1}{2\Delta t} \langle (\Delta x)^2 \rangle + \frac{1}{\Delta t} \sum_{j=2}^{\infty} \langle \Delta x_1 \Delta x_j \rangle \quad (4)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes an average over all considered sites and Δx_i denotes the displacement of a particle in the x direction at timestep i .

In off-lattice systems, $\langle \Delta x_1 \Delta x_j \rangle$ would be calculated by generating random trajectories for a number of particles starting from different starting points. This could be applied to the case of a lattice but would be highly inefficient as a very large number of trajectories would have to be generated to obtain good statistics in the very heterogeneous systems we are interested in here. Indeed, the lattice sites can have very different energies. We thus use a different approach, namely the so-called ‘moment propagation’ method, which was proposed by Frenkel and successfully applied to a number of studies on dynamics of particles in confined systems [10–12].

The moment-propagation method is a recursive scheme that allows one to sample *all* possible trajectories of the diffusing particles at the same time. The computational effort consequently scales linearly with the simulation time t and the number of lattice sites M . It is worth noting that the computational effort to sample all trajectories in a non-recursive scheme would scale as $z^t M$ with z is the coordination number of the lattice.

2.4 Application of the moment-propagation approach to the calculation of diffusion coefficients

In the expression for diffusion coefficients, the first term of equation 4 is easily calculated as it is equal to $1/2\Delta t$ times the mean-square displacement of a particle in the x direction during one timestep:

$$\frac{1}{2\Delta t} \langle (\Delta x)^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{2z\Delta t} \sum_{j=1}^z p_{acc}(i \rightarrow j) a_x^2(j) \quad (5)$$

where a_x is the x -component of the vector joining a lattice site to its j -th neighbour and the sum runs over all sites j adjacent i (note that $p_{acc}(i \rightarrow j) = 0$ if j is occupied by an obstacle).

The second term can be calculated using a recursive scheme. Consider Figure 2. It is convenient to introduce the notation $\langle \Delta x(j) \rangle_1$ for

$$\langle \Delta x(j) \rangle_1 \equiv \frac{1}{z} \sum_{\langle kj \rangle} p_B(k) p_{acc}(k \rightarrow j) \Delta \mathbf{x}_{kj}, \quad (6)$$

where $\langle kj \rangle$ denotes that k is a nearest neighbour of j . Then the contribution to the correlation function $\langle \Delta \mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \Delta \mathbf{x}_2 \rangle$ for site 1 is the weighted average over all neighbours of site 1 of the product $\Delta \mathbf{x}_{1j} \cdot \langle \Delta x(j) \rangle_1$ (see Fig 2(B)). Figure 2(C) and (D) show examples of the subsequent steps.

Figure 2: Consider a particle starting a random walk at site $i = 1$ (A). The probability of finding this particle in site i is given by the normalised Boltzmann weight $p_B(i) = ce^{-\beta U(i)}$. In one timestep, the particle can move with a probability $\frac{1}{z} p_{acc}(1 \rightarrow j)$ to any of the neighbouring sites j . For simplicity, we consider only site $j = 2$, but the same arguments apply to all z neighbours of 1. The displacement vector corresponding to the step from site 1 to site $j = 2$ is $\Delta \mathbf{x}_{12}$. To correlate $\Delta \mathbf{x}_{12}$ with the subsequent displacement vector starting at 2, we have to compute the average $\langle \Delta \mathbf{x}_2 \rangle \equiv \sum_{k=1}^z \frac{1}{z} p_{acc}(2 \rightarrow k) \Delta \mathbf{x}_{2k}$ (i.e. the weighted sum over the dark arrows shown in (B)). To get the complete contribution to the correlation function, we have to average the contributions of all z sites neighbouring site 1. To obtain $\langle \Delta \mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \Delta \mathbf{x}_3 \rangle$, we have to repeat the same procedure for all sites that can be reached in two steps from site 1, e.g. site 3 (see (C)). Similarly, to obtain $\langle \Delta \mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \Delta \mathbf{x}_4 \rangle$, we must consider all sites that can be reached in three steps from site 1, e.g. site 4.

To obtain the contribution to the correlation function due to site i , we compute:

$$\langle \Delta \mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \Delta \mathbf{x}_2 \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{1}{z} \sum_{\langle ji \rangle} p_{acc}(j \rightarrow i) \Delta \mathbf{x}_{ji} \cdot \langle \Delta \mathbf{x}(j) \rangle_1 \quad (7)$$

Continuing the recursive procedure, we define $\langle \Delta \mathbf{x}(j) \rangle_2$ as the average of the one-step displacement vector $\langle \Delta \mathbf{x}(k) \rangle_1$ of all particles that can reach site j in two steps from a site k . The contribution to the correlation function is then

$$\frac{1}{z} \sum_{jn,ni} p_{acc}(j \rightarrow i) \Delta \mathbf{x}_{ji} \cdot \langle \Delta \mathbf{x}(j) \rangle_2 \quad (8)$$

to obtain the desired correlation function by multiplying the propagated vectors with $\frac{1}{z} p_{acc}(n-1 \rightarrow n) \Delta \mathbf{x}_{n-1,n}$, for all z neighbours of site n . In general, the expression for $\langle \Delta \mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \Delta \mathbf{x}_n \rangle$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Delta \mathbf{x}_1 \cdot \Delta \mathbf{x}_n \rangle &= \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{1}{z} \sum_{\langle ji \rangle} p_{acc}(j \rightarrow i) \\ &\times \sum_k \text{Prob}(k \rightarrow j; n-2) \Delta \mathbf{x}_{ji} \cdot \langle \Delta \mathbf{x}(k) \rangle_1 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\text{Prob}(k \rightarrow j; n-2)$ denotes the probability that a particle diffuses in $n-2$ steps from site k to site j .

Overall, this recursive method can be applied using stencil operations.

2.5 Calculations of NMR spectra

NMR spectroscopy probes the nuclear magnetic response of a sample whose magnetism is perturbed from equilibrium by a radio frequency pulse. After this pulse, the transverse magnetisation of the sample decays. The NMR signal measured during this decay is commonly referred to as the Free Induction Decay (FID). The NMR spectrum is obtained by Fourier transforming the FID signal. In a heterogeneous sample, different nuclei will experience different local magnetic fields and will therefore have different Larmor frequencies. As the nuclei diffuse, their environments, and hence their resonant frequencies, change. The FID signal is the superposition of the signals corresponding to all excited nuclei in the sample. For an ensemble of probed spins, the NMR signal is given by:

$$G(t) = \langle e^{i \int_0^t 2\pi \nu_0^i(t') dt'} \rangle \quad (10)$$

where $\nu_0^i(t)$ is the Larmor frequency corresponding to spin i at time t , and $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes an average over all spins. The spectrum is then obtained by Fourier transforming this signal following:

$$\mathcal{F}(k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt G(t) e^{-2i\pi kt}. \quad (11)$$

Using the same approach as for the calculation of the diffusion coefficients, we can discretise these expressions and estimate them by the moment-propagation method. As a consequence, the operations needed to calculate NMR spectra are also stencil operations.

The calculation of NMR spectra is an important motivation for the development of this lattice-gas model as i) NMR experiments are a great tool to explore electrolyte adsorption in porous carbons [13], including under an applied electric field [14], and ii) NMR experiments provide data for testing the accuracy of the model. Nevertheless, no additional details will be provided in this report regarding NMR spectra prediction as improving the accuracy of the model is out of scope of this report.

2.6 Additional considerations on diffusion

In a homogeneous fluid, successive jumps are uncorrelated and we have:

$$D = \frac{1}{2\Delta t} \langle (\Delta x)^2 \rangle \quad (12)$$

If the probability to jump to a neighbouring site is equal to one, then $D = a^2/(2d\Delta t)$, where a is the lattice spacing. However, we can reduce the probability that a particle carries out a jump. If we denote the probability that a particle stays on the same site by $1 - \alpha$, then

$$D = \alpha \frac{1}{2d\Delta t} a^2. \quad (13)$$

In systems where the diffusivity varies with position, we can define a factor $\alpha(ij)$ for every link between neighbouring lattice sites i and j . It is important to note that if the probability to jump from i to j is reduced, then the probability to jump from j to i should be reduced by the same factor, otherwise the equilibrium distribution over lattice sites would be changed from the Boltzmann distribution.

Currently, the factors reducing diffusion between sites are assigned in a somewhat arbitrary fashion leading to partly inaccurate diffusion coefficients. Improving the accuracy of the model are planned in other tasks of the MultiXscale project.

3 Implementation of LPC3D in PyStencils and integration in EESSI

As most of the operations needed to conduct simulations with the lattice-gas model are stencils, the use of PyStencils was an obvious choice. Indeed, it allows to generate highly efficient and scalable C++ and CUDA/HIP code from the mathematical description of the model.

3.1 Workflow of LPC3D

Figure 3 illustrates the main steps involved in conducting a calculation with the lattice-gas model. The first steps are related to the reading of input files which will be used to parametrise the model, according to the representation of a chosen system (given pore size distribution, electrolyte species, NMR parameters). The fields and arrays necessary for

Figure 3: Steps involved in conducting a calculation with the lattice-gas model.

the calculation are then created. Following this step, a period of equilibration can be realised or not depending on the user settings. In particular, the densities of electrolyte species on sites can be initially set equal to Boltzmann averages (see equation 2) or to any user-defined values. The equilibration stops if either the densities become constant or if the maximum number of iterations to reach equilibrium is attained. Next, the propagation step of the moment-propagation approach is conducted for all required quantities. Finally, properties of interest are written.

These various steps are detailed more below.

1. Reading Input and Initialization:

The software begins by reading the input file, which defines all the simulation parameters, such as system dimensions, timestep, number of steps to simulate, boundary conditions, and the user choice of computational environment. This configuration allows the software to automatically select between a CPU_OpenMP parallel execution or a GPU-based approach using Cuda. During initialization, ghost layers are created to handle periodic boundary conditions, and different blocks are defined as either electrode or bulk regions, providing the necessary structural framework for simulating complex systems like supercapacitors.

2. Create Fields and Arrays:

Based on the initialization settings, the software uses `PyStencils` to generate fields and arrays corresponding to various physical quantities, such as energies and velocities. These fields represent the spatial discretization of the simulation domain and are crucial for lattice-based calculations. `PyStencils` ensures efficient data handling and parallel updates, allowing the simulation to adapt to different configurations based on user input.

3. Equilibration Phase:

The equilibration phase employs `PyStencils` to update the local density at each lattice site until a steady-state distribution is achieved. In the context of supercapacitors, this step can model the fluid entering or leaving the nanopores of the electrode when a potential is applied. To check if equilibrium is reached, the densities at time t ($\rho_i(t)$) are compared to those at the next time step ($\rho_i(t+1)$). If the difference is below a defined threshold, the system is considered equilibrated and the software moves to the propagation phase. Otherwise, the loop continues until convergence is reached or a maximum number of steps is attained.

4. Propagation Phase:

Once equilibration is complete, the software proceeds to the propagation phase. Dynamic quantities are calculated based on the equilibrated fields. This stage involves time-dependent simulations, where the system evolves using the chosen backend — either ‘`NumPy`’ for Central Processing Unit (CPU) computations or ‘`CuPy`’ for Graphical Processing Unit (GPU) accelerated operations. During this phase, various properties such as `VACF`, and `FID` signals for NMR spectra are computed.

5. Output Files and Analysis:

After completing the propagation phase, the software generates comprehensive output files containing the calculated properties, including densities, diffusion coefficients and `VACF`. Additionally, NMR spectra are obtained through a Fourier transformation of the `FID` signals.

3.2 Challenges identified and support from technical experts

The first implementation of `LPC3D` using `PyStencils` only showed weak scalability. Following discussions with Rudolf Weeber from USTUTT and technical experts from the SURF team, we made several steps to improve the performance of the code.

- **Memory profiling:** We performed memory profiling, which confirmed the problem of large RAM taken by arrays and fields generated at the very beginning of the calculation. This being said, the performance tests, with some system sizes sufficient to fulfill the objectives of MultiXscale, could be conducted on standard nodes of the CALMIP supercomputing centre [15].
- **Rewriting of some of the operations:** Some of the sums in particular were not done in the most efficient way.

These steps have helped improving the speed of execution and the scalability.

3.3 Code performance

The code was tested on CPU and GPU nodes on the CALMIP supercomputing center [15]. The standard CPU nodes

Figure 4: Runtime and memory usage for calculations, using the LP3CD code, conducted on CPU nodes exclusively and for various numbers of lattice sites.

have 36 cores and 192 GB of RAM. The GPU nodes have 36 cores, 4 GPUs and 384 GB of RAM. System sizes going

from $50 \times 50 \times 50$ (125,000 sites) to $700 \times 700 \times 700$ (343 million sites) have been considered. It is worth noting that with the initial serial implementation of LPC3D, before MultiXscale, only systems of size $30 \times 30 \times 30$ (27,000 sites) were routinely simulated. Systems of sizes up to $50 \times 50 \times 50$ could be simulated but not to explore a large amount of parameters.

Figure 4 shows runtime and RAM usage for calculations done exclusively on CPU. The calculations reported here were done with 36 processes. The runtime and memory usage confirm the linear scaling expected from the stencil operations conducted and from the memory usage being due to information stored for all lattice sites. While the runtime is long for large number of lattice sites, several thousands of timesteps can usually be simulated in a day.

Figure 5 shows the results of strong scaling tests. We report the speedup (i.e. acceleration) observed when the calculation is done on Np processes compared to 1 process. Calculations were conducted for two different system sizes (1 million sites and 343 million sites). The speedup is good for numbers of processes up to 16-20 but less good for

Figure 5: Evaluation of strong scaling performance of the LP3CD code. The dashed line indicate the ideal behaviour which would be observed if the code was perfectly parallel.

larger numbers. It is interesting to see that the scaling is better for larger numbers of sites.

It is worth noting that while LPC3D cannot use a larger number of processes, it will be coupled with other software to calculate more accurately the evolution of quantities in each lattice site (Tasks 3.3 and 4.2). A simulation will then require the realisation of a very large ensemble of molecular simulations in parallel which will use many cores.

Figure 6: Comparison between CPU and GPU calculation times for systems of various sizes.

Figure 6 shows the comparison between CPU and GPU runtimes for systems of various sizes. For small numbers of

lattice sites, the calculation times are similar. For larger system sizes, the calculation is much faster on GPU. The runtime for GPU also seems to be scaling linearly with the number of lattice sites.

Overall the performance of the implemented LPC3D software is satisfactory. The aim in MultiXscale was to go from systems of size $30 \times 30 \times 30$, that corresponds to a dimension of approximately $1 \mu\text{m}^3$, i.e. the size of a single - relatively small - particle, to systems where at least one dimension is a few hundreds of μm . With the current implementation, asymmetrical systems with around $1,000 \mu\text{m}$ to $5,000 \mu\text{m}$ in length and reasonable dimensions (sufficient considering periodic boundary conditions) can be simulated. Since the experimental thickness of electrodes is usually between 200 to $500 \mu\text{m}$, the current implementation allows to simulate a full supercapacitor with two electrodes and bulk areas with realistic dimensions. Increasing the size of the system would require going to a multi-node implementation, which would correspond to a relatively important effort as this cannot be done using `PyStencils` for the code generation, but does not seem necessary. This implementation is thus considered satisfactory.

3.4 Code release and integration with EESSI

As mentioned in the introduction, LPC3D is now available as an open-source code, along with a user manual, at <https://github.com/multixscale/LPC3D>.

The technical experts have integrated `PyStencils` in EESSI so that it is already very easy to install LPC3D. Work is ongoing to set up a GitHub CI workflow that uses the [EESSI GitHub Action](#) to add in the development of LPC3D and facilitate the full integration into EESSI.

4 Example of simulations with the new implementation of LPC3D

To illustrate what a simulation of full supercapacitor looks like, we have conducted calculations for a $50 \times 50 \times 250$ system. Figure 7 shows the supercapacitor made of two electrodes immersed in an electrolyte, i.e. there is electrolyte on two sides of the electrodes. The calculations were done with 36 processes on a standard node of the CALMIP supercomputing center [15]. The calculation time for 50,000 steps (necessary for NMR spectra prediction) is 22 minutes. In this case, the presence of electrolyte on both sides of the electrodes allow us to apply periodic boundary conditions in all directions.

Figure 7: Illustration of the simulation of a full supercapacitor using LPC3D. The pictures were made using paraview [16]. Two monolithic electrodes are immersed in an electrolyte. Calculations for two applied potentials, 0V and 2V, are conducted. The color scale corresponds to the concentration of anions. In the bulk, the concentration is maximum. In the pores of the electrodes, there are less ions, due to the pore sizes and confinement. The application of a potential, creates, as expected, differences between concentrations in the positive and negative electrodes.

The specific system studied is BMIM-BF₄ (1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate) in acetonitrile in contact with carbon monoliths (i.e. there are no particles, the carbon is taking all the space of the electrodes). The electrodes are parametrised with the same pore size distributions and energies as the ones used in reference [3]. Two potentials, 0V and 2V, are considered.

The concentration of the anions in the different parts of the supercapacitor are shown as a color scale. As expected, the concentration is maximum in the bulk and smaller in the pores of the electrodes. The existence of different pore sizes leads to different ion concentrations, giving the pixellate representation. When the potential applied is 0V, while the spatial distribution of pore sizes (generated randomly) is not exactly the same in the two electrodes, the concentration pattern is very similar. When the potential applied is 2V, more anions are present in the positive electrode than in the negative electrode, in agreement with adsorption energies.

Diffusion coefficients were also evaluated in different parts of the system, as allowed by the software. The diffusion coefficients in the pores are smaller than in the bulk, ranging from $0.07 \times D_{bulk}$ to $0.8 \times D_{bulk}$, and depend on the electrode potential.

Conducting further analyses on this system is out of scope of this report.

5 Conclusion and perspectives

This report presents the implementation and testing of a lattice-gas model, `LPC3D`, which is used to simulate electrolyte species diffusion in porous carbons and in full supercapacitors. The code, implemented serially in C before the MultiXscale project, was reimplemented in C++ using the `PyStencils` code generator. **The new version of `LPC3D` is orders of magnitude faster and allows to simulate systems several thousand times larger than the initial code.** The performance tests show that the runtime and memory usage scale, as expected from the equations of the model, linearly with the number of sites. The strong scaling on a single HPC node is quite good, especially for large numbers of lattice sites.

The multi-node implementation, that we considered doing to deal with memory usage, actually seems unnecessary at this point since we have reached the objectives stated for the MultiXscale project. In particular, we can now do calculations on full supercapacitors with electrode having realistic thicknesses compared to this experiments.

The perspectives of this work are thus to move towards the coupling between this mesoscopic model and molecular simulations to improve the accuracy of the representation of electrolyte species in the pores. This is described in Tasks 3.3 and 4.2 of the MultiXscale project. Indeed, the adsorption energies and energy barriers, related to diffusion, are currently parametrised through a single molecular dynamics simulation which is not optimal, especially for nanopores. Couplings with molecular DFT and molecular dynamics simulations will be set-up concomitantly. The coupling with molecular dynamics simulations should be relatively straightforward while the coupling with molecular DFT is more challenging but would lead to a better computing efficiency. **The on-the-fly calculation of properties in each lattice site from molecular simulations will require the realisation of a large ensemble of simulations which can be conducted in parallel exploiting the resources of supercomputers.**

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References

Acronyms used

HPC	High Performance Computing
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CPU	Central Processing Unit
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
MDFT	Molecular Density Functional Theory
DFT	Density Functional Theory
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
FID	Free Induction Decay
VACF	Velocity AutoCorrelation Functions

Software mentioned

ESPResSo Extensible Simulation Package for Research on Soft Matter Systems

LAMMPS Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator

LPC3D Lattice Porous Carbon 3D

URLs referenced

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<https://www.multixscale.eu> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu>
<https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables>
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